

**DAWAT PROGRAM (Doors of Opportunity, Acceptance of Oneself, Working Together, Amidst Challenges for Transforming Lives of the learners):
FOR SCHOOL LIFE OF LEARNERS WITH SPECIAL NEEDS**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10929617>

ABSTRACT

The study proposed a Dawat Program that may address the school life of the learners with special needs. The respondents were selected through purposive sampling technique from Grade 7 to Grade 12 who were officially enrolled in Lun Padidu National High School for this School Year 2023-2024. Survey guide questionnaire was utilized in generating data on the academic performance and social behavior of the respondents in order to give emphasis in the quantitative aspect of this endeavor. Further, survey guide questions were used in getting information on the experiences of the participants in school as a complementary to the quantitative data collected. Percentage, mean and general point average were utilized in analyzing the numerical data gathered and thematic analysis for the experiences of the participants. The findings revealed that only 1 or 14.3% out of 7 respondents got Very Satisfactory academic performance and 6 or 85.7% got Fairly Satisfactory. Further, the respondents were Fairly Sociable in dealing with their classmates and Not Sociable in dealing with their teachers. They have limited friends in school, very low self-confidence, experienced discrimination and bullying from their classmates and schoolmates. For this, the researchers were eager to propose a DAWAT program in order to address the gaps identified in this endeavor that may help the participants with special needs enhance their potentials as learners, human beings, and citizens of this country by catering them in activities such as sports or indoor games, arts and music, social activities and spiritual aspect for the purpose of giving them value and importance and attention in addressing their needs.

Keywords: *Dawat Program, Special Needs, Social Behavior, Academic Performance*

INTRODUCTION

Having a disability can be one of the most marginalizing factors in a child's life. In education, finding ways to meet the learning needs of students with disabilities can be challenging, especially in schools, districts, regions, and countries with severely limited resources. Inclusive education—which fully engages all students, including students with disabilities or other learning challenges, in quality education—has proven particularly effective in helping all students learn, even while challenges to implementing inclusive education systems remain. This guide provides suggestions for developing inclusive education systems and policies, especially for low- and middle-income countries that are moving from a segregated system toward an inclusive system of education.

Disability is present in every race, ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, age, and religion. More than a billion people, or 15 percent of the world's population, have some category of disability. Of these, an estimated 150 million children have a disability, and 80 percent of these children live in the developing world (Bulat et al., 2017). These children often face conditions of extreme poverty, exclusion, and discrimination and are denied the basic services offered to their peers without disabilities. The United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) estimates that 90 percent of children with disabilities in low-income countries have never received any form of education (UNICEF, 2014).

In Lun Padidu National High School, there were 38 students who have special needs specifically in their physical, mental, or even speech impairment. Further, majority of the learners with special needs affirmed that they had trouble in coping up their lessons, they don't have friends in school, they do not participate in class discussions because of their low self-confidence, and they were quite all the time and always get bored.

Thus, based on the problems identified, it ignited the interest of the researchers to pursue this endeavor to come up with an intervention to address the gaps identified in this study by developing a "DAWAT" program that may give participants a sense of belongingness and giving them importance and value as learners, as human beings, and citizens of this country.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study determined the school life of the learners with special needs of Lun Padidu National High School. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. How is the school life of learners with special needs in Lun Padidu National High School in terms of:
 - 1.1 Academic performance;
 - 1.2 Social behavior
 - 1.2.1 Classmates; and

1.2.2 Teachers?

2. What are the experiences of the learners with special needs in school?
3. What intervention could be developed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

The research design was a qualitative in nature where the purposive sampling technique in choosing the participants who were the learners with special needs was utilized. Before data gathering, the researchers asked first the permission from the Schools Division Superintendent by sending a letter of permission to conduct the study. After that, the researchers sent a letter to the school head.

The survey guide questionnaire was utilized in the generation of data on the academic performance and social behavior of the respondents. While interview guide questions were used which contained questions about the school life of learners with special needs.

This study used descriptive design which investigated the school life of the participants in terms of their academic performance and social behavior as well as their experiences in school in general.

It utilized the Colaizzi's method of analyzing qualitative data in which to employ rigorous data collection procedures, to frame the study within the assumptions and characteristics of the qualitative approach research, tradition of inquiry begin with simple focus, includes detailed methods, rigorous approach, to data collection, data analysis, and report writing, to write persuasively so that the reader experiences "being there" or verisimilitude, analyze data using multiple levels of abstraction, the writing is clear, engaging, and full of unexpected ideas.

The researchers focused for participants who were close to the inclusion criteria. Seven learners with special needs were included for the purposive sampling as set in the inclusion standard. In this study, the researchers set the criteria on how to analyze and interpret the data.

General Point Average, frequency, and percentage were utilized in analyzing the academic performance of the participants while weighted mean was used in analyzing the social behavior of them. Thus, the thematic analysis was used in analyzing their experiences in school.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF THE STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL NEEDS

Using the document analysis in generating data, the academic performance of the student-respondents is presented below:

Table 1. Academic Performance of the Respondents

Grade	f (n=7)	%	Description
90-100	0	0	Outstanding
85-89	1	14.3	Very Satisfactory
80-84	0	0	Satisfactory
75-79	6	85.7	Fairly Satisfactory
74 and below	0	0	Did not Meet Expectations

The table 1 above shows the academic performance of the respondents.

It further shows that only 1 or 14.3% out of 7 respondents has a very satisfactory academic performance while 6 or 85.7% of the respondents got a fairly satisfactory academic performance.

Thus, the data show that majority of the learners with special needs are not performing academically wherein they did not perform the required competencies in specific curriculum.

The table 2 on the next page shows the social behavior of the respondents in dealing with their classmates. It further shows that the learners with special needs collaborated with their classmates during class activities with a weighted mean of 1.7 which described as Fairly Sociable. Further, they shared their ideas or thoughts with their classmates on any projects or assignments with a weighted mean of 1.5 which described as Fairly Sociable. They spent time with their classmates in school during their free time with a weighted mean of 1.43 which described as Fairly Sociable.

Table 2. Social Behavior of the Respondents in Dealing with their Classmates

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Description
1. Communicate with their classmates in school.	1.39	Not Sociable
2. Collaborated with their classmates during class activities.	1.7	Fairly Sociable

3. Shared personal experiences/problems with their classmates	1.2	Not Sociable
4. Shared ideas or thoughts with their classmates on any projects or assignments.	1.5	Fairly Sociable
5. Spent time with their classmates in school during free time.	1.43	Fairly Sociable
Total	1.44	Fairly Sociable

The table 2 in the previous page shows the social behavior of the respondents in dealing with their classmates. It further shows that the learners with special needs collaborated with their classmates during class activities with a weighted mean of 1.7 which described as Fairly Sociable. Further, they shared their ideas or thoughts with their classmates on any projects or assignments with a weighted mean of 1.5 which described as Fairly Sociable. They spent time with their classmates in school during their free time with a weighted mean of 1.43 which described as Fairly Sociable.

However, they did not share their personal experiences/problems with their classmates with a weighted mean of 1.2 which described as Not Sociable. They did not also share their personal experiences/problems with their classmates.

It is noted that the learners with special needs are not sociable, they kept themselves alone or away from their classmates specifically during collaborative work activities.

Thus, it is a need for the school to formulate a program that would cater, accept, value and give importance to them in order to enhance and boost their self-confidence to pursue their progress and development in social aspect of their lives.

The table 3 in the latter page shows the social behavior of the respondents in dealing with their teachers. It further shows that they never talked with their teachers regarding on their performance in school. They also never communicate with their teachers, Further, they did not share their experiences with their teachers and never asked assistance from their teachers relating to projects and assignments.

Indeed, it is a need for teachers to check the status or conditions of their learners with special needs. They would give time to talk with them which generally show their sympathy and concern toward them.

Table 3. Social Behavior of the Respondents in Dealing with their Teachers

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Description
1. Communicate with their teachers.	1.35	Not Sociable
2. Talked with their teachers regarding on their performance.	1.30	Not Sociable
3. Shared their life experiences with their teachers.	1.27	Not Sociable
4. Asked advises from their class adviser/teachers relating to personal life.	1.0	Not Sociable
5. Asked assistance from their teachers relating to projects and assignments.	1.0	Not Sociable
Total	1.18	Not Sociable

Experiences of the Learners with Special Needs in School.

From the interview conducted with the participants with special needs on their experiences in school revealed four essential themes such as having limited friends, have very low self-confidence, experienced discrimination, and experienced bullying.

Table 4. Themes and Thematic Statements on the Experiences of the Learners with Special Needs in school.

Essential Themes	Thematic Statements
A. Have Limited Friends	Majority of the learners with special needs have limited friends.
B. Very low self-confidence	All of the participants have very low self-confidence.
C. Experienced discrimination	Majority of the participants were discriminated by their peers.
D. Experienced Bullying	All participants were bullied by their peers and classmates.

Have Limited Friends

During the interview conducted where the researchers asked the 7 participants on their experiences in school, majority of the learners with special needs have limited friends as they confirmed.

SP-1: *I have only limited friends sir because we seldom talked with our classmates and school mates*

SP-2: *I don't have friends sir because I afraid and shy on them, maybe they will laugh at me, but it is alright sir, I accept it even if I hurt*

SP-3: *I have only two friends because nobody can accept me as their friend.*

SP-4: I do not have friend because I afraid to have friends.

SP-5 I never find friend because they cannot afford to have friend like me.

They said that they have limited friends in school because they often communicate with their classmates and school mates because of their being shy to be with them.

Very Low Self-confidence

All of the participants have very low self-confidence as they confirmed.

SP-1: *I have a very low self-confidence Ma'am because of my disability, I am shy to perform the tasks because I afraid that they may laugh at me*

SP-2: I have a very low self-confidence Ma'am and that because of my disability. I never recited to teachers because I afraid to be bullied by someone else.

SP-3: I do not participate in class discussion because I afraid to be bullied by someone else.

SP-4: I am not asking questions to my teachers because I cannot open my mouth, instead, I just keep quiet.

SP-5: I am shy to participate in school activities because of my condition

SP-6: I never tried volunteer myself to lead in our group activities because of my condition.

SP-7: I did not try to become a leader in any activities in school due to being shy.

It is noted that the student-participants have low self-confidence because of their condition.

Experienced Discrimination

Majority of the participants were discriminated by their peers as they confirmed.

SP-1: I had experienced discrimination Ma'am from my classmates if we have group activities or projects made by group. Sometimes, I could ask why I exist in this world.

SP-3: My classmates discriminated me especially during group activities.

SP-4: I have experienced discrimination with my schoolmates where they disregard my request in school related activities.

SP-6: My classmates did not include me during group discussions.

Experienced Bullying

All participants were bullied by their peers and classmates.

SP-1: I cannot forget that a lot of students bullied me, sometimes, I cried because I really hurt on the words, they talked about me.

SP-2: I had experienced bullying from my schoolmates especially if I walked inside of this campus, they laughed at me.

SP-3: Yes, my schoolmates laugh at me when they saw me walking.

SP-4: I had bullied my classmates in times of group activities because of my capacity.

SP-5: My schoolmates bullied my condition by teasing me.

SP-6: My classmates bullied me due to my learning capability as they told me unpleasant words.

SP-7: I always cried at school because my classmates bullied me on my personality.

Generally, majority of the participants with special needs have low academic performance, limited friends, low self-confidence, not participative in class discussions, and experienced bullying from their schoolmates and classmates.

Indeed, there is a need for the teachers to give attention on the status of these learners with special needs by constantly communicate with them. They should be vigilant in looking into the needs of these learners. For this reason, the researchers recommend that the DAWAT program consists of activities to be done should be implemented to address the needs of the learners where this program consists of activities that may transform the learners with special needs into joyful, interested and motivated or excited in going to school that may boost their self-confidence, improve their social aspect,

enhance their talents and interests that may pursue the development of their life as a whole.

INTERVENTION PROGRAM

This study determined the school life of the learners with special needs which was the basis in the formulation of the intervention entitled, “DAWAT Program” or **D**oors of Opportunity, **A**ccceptance of Oneself, **W**orking Together, **A** midst Challenges for **T**ransforming Lives of the learners with Special Needs. This intervention will help the identified learners in their development relating to school life. Specifically, this intervention will be implemented to school every last Friday of the month. The activities will cover the arts and music, spiritual, sports specifically indoor games, and social activities that may transform their being bored into fulfillment of joy because of the recreational activities of this program. Thus, these activities will cater the learners with special needs for the purpose of holistic development of them that may transform their lives in school by accepting them as learners, human beings, and citizens of this country by giving them a chance to enjoy and feel valued as a family in school through of these activities.

Furthermore, this DAWAT Program will be implemented through the following processes and procedures. First, the action plan as well as the letter of permission to cater this program in school will be handed or presented to the school principal. As soon as the principal approved the request of implementation, the conference with the teachers will be the next step to do. The orientation and discussion with regards to how this program be implemented will be given emphasis. After the conference with the school faculty, the organization of the teacher in-charge of the specific area like sports, arts and music, sports or indoor games and social activities, as the focus of this program should be organized. Since the organization of the committee has been made, the implementation of this DAWAT Program will be consistently done every last Friday of the month wherein these students who have special needs will be catered according to their field of interest. Those who have talents in sports or indoor games, they would join in that activity, while those who have interested in arts and music, they have to join in that specific activity, the social activities will be catered also as well as the spiritual activities that may develop the students with special needs’ potentials, talents, and skills.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Most of the respondents were fairly satisfactory, they were fairly sociable that have limited friends and seldom communicated with their family.

2. They have very low self-confidence, experience discrimination and bullying from their classmates and schoolmates.
3. The students are not sociable in dealing with their teachers.

Recommendations

1. The researchers recommend this intervention to be implemented to school every last Friday of the month. The activities will cover the arts and music, spiritual, sports specifically indoor games, and social activities that may transform their being bored into fulfillment of joy because of the recreational activities of this program.
2. It is a need for teachers to check the status or conditions of their learners with special needs. They would give time to talk with them which generally show their sympathy and concern toward them.
3. It is a need for the school to formulate a program that would cater, accept, value and give importance to them in order to enhance and boost their self-confidence to pursue their progress and development in social aspect of their lives.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors had emphasized to the participants that they don't have conflicts of interest regarding the research, authorship, and/or publication of this endeavor. The authors were accomplished this study in compliance with the research ethics protocol. Informed consent was given to each participant before the conduct of the study. The data were treated with utmost confidentiality.

Acknowledgement

The researchers were very thankful for the following who contributed for the success of this endeavor. First, to almighty God who bestowed them knowledge and perseverance in pursuing this study, all praises unto him. Second, to the school principal of Lun Padidu National High School, for giving them an opportunity to present this undertaking. Lastly, to the respondents who untiringly responded during the data

gathering. From the bottom of their hearts, the researchers gave their great gratitude for the good deeds they contributed.

REFERENCES

BULAT, J. & HAYES, A. (2017). Disabilities inclusions systems and policies guide for low-and-middle-income countries. National Library and Medicine.

UNICEF (2014). International disability and development Consortium.<https://www.iddconsortium.net/https://www.unicef.org/reports/unicef-annual-report-2014>.